

Synthesis, spectral and microbial studies of 4-salicyldimino-3-phenyl/methyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole and their complexes with Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}

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Abstract : The stable complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} with (O, N, S) donor triazole derivatives, viz. 4-salicyldimino-3-methyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (H₂salmtr) and 4-salicyldimino-3-phenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (H₂salptr) of composition [M(HL)₂] (M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} or Cd^{II} and H₂L = H₂salmtr and H₂salptr) as well as [MLB] (M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} or Cd^{II} and B = H₂O or Py) have been prepared, analysed and their probable structure have been suggested from the studies of magnetic susceptibility, electrical conductance, IR data and electronic absorption spectral measurements. The bischelate [M(HL)₂] (M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II} and H₂L = H₂salmtr and H₂salptr) shows UV spectral and magnetic moment values consistent with distorted octahedral geometry. The Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} bischelates and monoligated complexes [MLB] (M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and H₂L = H₂salmtr or H₂salptr) are four coordinated tetrahedral while [NiLB] and [CuLB] (B = H₂O or Py and H₂L = H₂salmtr or H₂salptr) are planar. The Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes and ligands were screened for some antibacterial activity. The antimicrobial properties followed the order : H₂salmtr < H₂salptr < Zn^{II} < Cd^{II} < Cu^{II} (bischelates). The antifungal activity of [CdLPy] and [CuLPy] was greater than ZnLPy.

Keywords : Synthesis, characterisation and microbial studies, 4-salicyldimino-3-alkyl/aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole, bivalent metal complexes.

Introduction

The Schiff bases of triazole derivatives and their metal complexes possess potential pharmacological properties¹⁻⁸. It is found that medicinal potentiality of ligand is enhanced ridiculously on coordination with appropriate metal ions⁶. In view of potential drug activity and our interest to study the complexes of triazole derivatives⁹⁻¹², we here report the synthesis, characterisation and antibacterial activity of the complexes of some bivalent metal ions with 4-salicyldimino-3-methyl/phenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole.

Results and discussion

4-Salicyldimino-3-methyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (H₂salmtr) and 4-salicyldimino-3-phenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (H₂salptr) (Fig. A) are potent O, N, S donor ligands and coordinate as mono anionic ligand in neutral

Fig. A. (R = -CH₃ or -C₆H₅)

weakly or acid medium but as dianionic coordinating molecule in basic medium.

The elemental analysis of complexes, formed in neutral or weakly acid solution (pH 4-6), correspond to composition [M(HL)₂].nH₂O (M = Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}, H₂L = H₂salmtr or H₂salptr and n = 0 whereas n = 2 for Ni^{II}). The complexes formed in basic medium, pyridine or dilute ammonia (pH 8-9) correspond to composi-

tion [MLB] ($M = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ and Cd^{II} , $\text{H}_2\text{L} = \text{H}_2\text{salptr}$ or H_2salmtr and $\text{B} = \text{H}_2\text{O}$ or Py). The bischelates $[\text{M}(\text{HL})_2] \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are usually insoluble in water but dissolve slightly in ethanol or methanol. The DMF solutions of both $[\text{M}(\text{HL})_2] \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and [MLB] display negligible electrical conductance value ($6\text{--}12 \Omega^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$) suggesting nonionic character of complexes¹³. The bisligated nickel(II) complexes, $[\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{LH}_2 = \text{H}_2\text{salmtr}$ or H_2salptr), on heating in air oven lose weight below 110°C equivalent to $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ indicating them to be uncoordinated while monoligated complexes $[\text{ML}(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ ($M = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ or Cd^{II} , $\text{LH}_2 = \text{H}_2\text{salptr}$ or H_2salmtr) retained H_2O even at $120\text{--}130^\circ\text{C}$ and then slowly lose H_2O with change in colour of the complexes indicating their coordination with metal atoms. The complexes are stable below $280\text{--}320^\circ\text{C}$ and on further heating they start decomposing with gradual loss in weight yielding tarry mass. The bischelates of $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ and Cu^{II} are paramagnetic and those of $\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}$ and $[\text{NiLB}]$ ($M = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ or Cd^{II}) are diamagnetic. The magnetic moment value at 304 K are 3.12 and 3.21 B.M. for $[\text{Ni}(\text{HL})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 1.84 and 1.86 for $[\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2]$ ($\text{LH} = \text{H}_2\text{salmtr}$ and H_2salmtr) suggested their octahedral structure¹⁴. The magnetic moment value 2.93 B.M. for $[\text{Co}(\text{Hsalptr})_2]$ and 3.12 B.M. for $[\text{Co}(\text{Hsalptr})_2]$ indicated exchange interaction in spin states and possess octahedral structure^{14c}. The electronic absorption spectra of $[\text{Co}(\text{HL})_2]$ in DMF do not display distinct electronic transition probably weak absorption expected for octahedral geometry is eclipsed in strong charge transfer transitions. The copper(II) complexes $[\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2]$ and $[\text{CuLPy}]$ display strong absorption below 430 nm attributed to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and weak broad shoulder at $630\text{--}680\text{ nm}$ attributed from ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions^{15,16}. The electronic absorption bands of $[\text{NiLPy}]$ were very strong below 400 nm and a broad shoulder near $450\text{--}470\text{ nm}$ in DMF solution. The electronic transition at $450\text{--}470\text{ nm}$ in DMF solution is assigned to be ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transition in planar field¹⁷ and former to charge transfer band.

The IR spectra of ligands and their complexes in KBr disc, display broad medium IR bands near 2960 to 3250 cm^{-1} . The IR band near $3050\text{--}3250$ of H_2salmtr is attributed to $\nu(\text{C-H})$ of phenyl, $\nu(\text{N-H})$ triazole and hydrogen bonded $\nu(\text{OH})$ of phenolic group of salicyladimino substituent. The IR spectra of H_2salmtr displays medium band

near $1624, 1595$ and 1572 cm^{-1} attributed to $\nu(\text{C=N})$ of aldimine group, $\nu(\text{C=N})$ and $\delta(\text{NH})$ of triazole ring respectively.

The aldimino group $\nu(\text{C=N})$ vibration of H_2salmtr is shifted to lower wave number in complexes due to coordination with metal atom. The triazole group (C=N) nitrogen and triazole ring skeletal vibrations were observed in finger print region located at $1572, 1482, 1368, 1306, 1282, 1125, 1025, 930, 830, 745$ and 688 cm^{-1} for H_2salmtr . The phenolic group $\nu(\text{C-O})$ of ligands were assigned to IR bands at 1125 cm^{-1} (H_2salmtr) and at 1182 cm^{-1} for H_2salptr and these are shifted to higher wave number in complexes by ($100\text{--}150\text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicating the coordination of deprotonated phenolic oxygen. The aqua complexes $[\text{ML}(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ ($M = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ or Cd^{II} and $\text{H}_2\text{L} = \text{H}_2\text{salmtr}$ or H_2salptr) display broad band at $3020\text{--}3340\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $\nu(\text{H}_2\text{O})$, $\nu(\text{CH}_3)$ and $\nu(\text{C-H})$ phenyl group. A new broad band at $670\text{--}690\text{ cm}^{-1}$ of aqua complexes assigned as rocking $\rho_w(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ of coordinated water¹⁷. The $\nu(\text{C=S})$ of H_2salmtr was observed at 930 cm^{-1} which is shifted to lower frequency by $30\text{--}40\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in neutral bischelate but $160\text{--}180\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes with dianionic ligands suggesting the coordination of thione sulphur in former and deprotonated thiol sulphur in later. The $\nu(\text{C=S})$ of H_2salptr was observed at 962 cm^{-1} that is shifted to $25\text{--}30\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in bisligated complexes $\text{M}(\text{Hsalptr})_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ indicating the coordination in thione sulphur of (C=S) group. The $\nu(\text{C=S})$ of H_2salptr is shifted by $160 \pm 30\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes with dianionic form of ligands indicating coordination through deprotonated thiol sulphur¹⁷. A large number of IR band in finger print regions observed in H_2salptr located at $1565, 1473, 1453, 1384, 1318, 1281, 1105, 840, 746$ and 635 cm^{-1} are not affected appreciably in complexes but get broadend due to complex formation¹⁷.

The antibacterial studies of ligands and their complexes were performed by disc diffusion method at 1 mg/ml disc concentration¹⁸. The nutrient agar medium was prepared taking 5 g peptone, 5 g beef extract, 5 g NaCl and 20 g agar agar dissolved in one litre distilled water. The solution was pipeted into Petri plate dried and added seeded agar with bacteria. The compound was taken in DMF 1 mg/ml disc concentration. The discs of Whatman no. 1 filter paper soaked with the solution was dried and placed on the medium previously seeded with organism in Petri plate at a suitable distance. The Petri plate were stored in an incubator at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h . The zone

Note

of inhibition was formed around each disc. The zone of inhibition was measured accurately in millimetre. The percentage inhibition was calculated. The bacteria tested for *in vitro* growth inhibitory activity were screened for *S. epidermis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC 737) (*S. aureus*) (these are Gram-positive bacteria) and two Gram-negative bacteria, *P. aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli* (MTCC 1687) (*E. coli*) and Ampicilline (17–22 mm zone of inhibition) was taken as standard. The comparison of zone of inhibition of some compounds and ligands are shown in Table 1. The zone of inhibition indicated large antibacterial activity for Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes than those of free ligand.

Experimental

The ligand H₂salmtr and H₂salptr were prepared by condensing 4-amino-3-methyl/phenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole with salicylaldehyde in dilute aqueous acetic acid medium by refluxing on a steam bath for two to three hours⁸. The triazole was prepared by reported method⁹. Metal salts, hydrazine hydrate, CS₂, salicylaldehyde and solvents were extra pure reagent of Nice or E. Merck. The magnetic susceptibility of complexes were determined by Gouy method and effective magnetic moment value were calculated making diamagnetic corrections using Pascals constant¹⁴. The electronic absorption spectra were recorded in ethanol or DMF on Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 15 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The other physico-chemical properties were recorded as reported earlier^{10,11}.

Preparation of complexes :

$M(HL)_2 \cdot nH_2O$ ($M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}$ or Cd^{II} , $n = 0$ and $H_2L = H_2salmtr$ or $H_2salptr$ and $n = 2$ for Ni^{II}) :

An aqueous ethanolic solution of ligand (0.02 mol in

30–40 ml 95% ethanol) was treated with aqueous ethanolic solution of metal acetate (0.01 mol) in 20–25 ml slowly with stirring. The mixed solutions were heated on steam bath for half an hour, when complexes separated on cooling. In a few cases, Ni^{II} complexes were obtained on diluting the solution with water. The complexes were filtered washed with cold aqueous ethanol and dried over CaCl₂. The Zn^{II} or Cd^{II} complexes are cream coloured, cobalt(II) complexes brown and nickel(II) complexes are greenish yellow in colour.

$[MLB]$ ($M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Cd^{II}$, $H_2L = H_2salmtr$ or $H_2salptr$ and $B = H_2O$ or Py) :

The aqueous ethanolic solution of 0.01 mol of ligand (in 25–30 ml) was treated with metal acetate solution (0.01 mol) in 20–25 ml hot ethanol, and the pH of hot solution was raised to 8–9 by ammonia or pyridine. The resulting coloured solution was heated for 30–45 min and cooled at room temperature when adduct or aqua complexes separated gradually. The products were collected on a filter, washed with cold water containing a few drop of pyridine. The complexes were dried over KOH in a desiccator. The complexes and ligands were analysed and their analytical result are in good agreement of proposed compositions. The antibacterial screening of ligands and complexes were performed for *S. aureus*, *S. epidermis*, *P. aeruginosa* and *E. coli*. The screening test were compared with Ampicilline as standard. The results are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Antibacterial activity

Compd.	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. epidermis</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
Ampicilline (std.) (mm)	22	20	20	21
H ₂ salmtr (mm)	12 (52%)	11 (50%)	10 (45%)	11 (50%)
H ₂ salptr (mm)	8 (35%)	10 (45%)	11 (50%)	11 (50%)
Co(Hsalmtr) ₂ (mm)	13 (59%)	14 (66%)	12 (60%)	12 (53%)
Co(Hsalptr) ₂ (mm)	12 (53%)	13 (65%)	12 (60%)	12 (53%)
Cu(Hsalmtr) ₂ (mm)	14 (63%)	12 (60%)	12 (60%)	13 (62%)
Cu(Hsalptr) ₂ (mm)	10 (45%)	10 (50%)	11 (55%)	12 (56%)
Cd(Hsalmtr) ₂ (mm)	13 (59%)	13 (65%)	11 (55%)	13 (62%)
		12 (60%)	12 (60%)	
Cd(Hsalptr) ₂ (mm)	9 (40%)	12 (60%)	11 (55%)	11 (52%)
Zn(H ₂ salmtr) ₂ (mm)	9 (40%)	10 (50%)	10 (50%)	11 (51%)

Conclusions

The Schiff bases usually coordinate as tridentate dianionic form in mono ligated complexes [MLB] forming bond with aldimine N and deprotonated thiol S and phenolic O atoms. But with $[M(LH)_2] \cdot nH_2O$, the ligands are bounded as N, S, O atom forming bond from thione sulphur atom. The screening test indicated higher activity of complexes than free ligand.

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